

HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM ECONOMY

Abdullabekova Noilaxon G'ofurjon qizi

Namangan State University

2nd-level student of hotel management and organization

Abstract: This article examines the role of tourism and hotel industry in the economy, the opinion of scientists on the management of the quality and efficiency of tourist services in hotels, observation, comparison, empirical research, systematic and comparative analysis, and statistical grouping and expert opinions about methods such as evaluation are presented

Key words: tourism industry, hotel industry, economy, infrastructure, restaurants, tour operator service, tourist

As the interest of the world's population to travel is increasing, the volume of visits of people from the territory of their own country to the territory of another country is also increasing. And this, in turn, is causing the emergence of a new industry in the world, that is, this industry is the "tourism industry". The tourism industry is an integrated system that includes many service industries. Hotels are the most important of such industries. In turn, regulating the activities of such an important sector requires a lot of responsibility. That is why we need to be able to apply marketing research and communications in this field.

In general, as in any industry, hotel marketing has several tasks:

- entering the market based on thorough and comprehensive study of consumer demand, taste and desire. Production of services that meet these requirements.
- increasing the socio-economic effectiveness of market relations that increase the market system of the service provider and reaching their most acceptable level, constantly expanding the types of services, actively searching for new markets (market segments), expanding existing markets.

Along with the increasing number of tourists to our republic, introducing them to the rich culture, traditions, history, lifestyle, national dishes and agricultural products of our people is widely underway. This, in turn, serves to increase the flow of tourists visiting the regions of our republic, to ensure the employment of the population in the field of tourism, and to increase the export of tourism services.

In the event that no less than 20 family guest houses are created in the areas of citizens' gatherings and at least five different types of services (except accommodation and/or catering services) are provided for tourists, they will receive "Tourism neighborhood", "Tourism village" or "Tourism farm" status. Starting from 2020, the citizens' assembly with the status of "Tourism neighborhood", "Tourism village" or "Tourism farm" will be included in the "Prosperous village" and "Prosperous neighborhood" state programs.

It will be beneficial for both parties if the hotels, in the process of carrying out their activities on the basis of a cluster, establish mutual cooperation with the Tourism neighborhood, village and farm. The hotel cluster is one of the entities of the tourism cluster, which aims to increase hotel revenues throughout the year, expand the range of services by establishing direct relations with tourists, and other entities in the field of tourism. by expanding cooperative relations, new enterprises serve to increase the tourism potential of the region by creating jobs (added value chain). It should be noted that currently there is no unified understanding among many authors regarding the category of hotel service quality, in particular, as an object of management. In our opinion, the quality of hotel services is a certain set of standards and a variety of services that customers expect to receive. , food, various additional and auxiliary services to meet the individual needs of clients defined in practice. From this point of view, quality has normative properties defined in relevant standards, quality can be compared only among similar

services, quality can be evaluated by each consumer based on socio-economic parameters and his personal preferences.

Research methodology. As a research methodology, methods such as observation, comparison, empirical research, systematic and comparative analysis, as well as statistical grouping and expert evaluation were used, studying the opinion of scientists regarding the management of the quality and efficiency of tourist services in hotels.

Analysis and results. Today, the hotel industry has become a powerful system of regional and country economy and an important component of the tourism economy. The hotel industry consists of many different public and individual accommodations of different classes, categories, types, hotels, hotels, motels, youth hotels and hostels, apartments, tourist villages, the private sector involved in the accommodation of tourists - home hotels, etc. includes. Hotel services have a number of unique features, knowing them and organizing and managing services on this basis allows to increase the quality and efficiency of hotel services and income. These and many other aspects are known to most professionals and depend mainly on the following characteristics of hotel services:

1) Simultaneous occurrence of production and consumption processes of services and products. The provision of hotel services requires the active participation of both the consumer and the performer, such services take place on the territory of the performer. The service employee is in direct contact with the consumer, and the consumer considers the executive employee to be an integral part of the hotel service. The quality of hotel services is largely evaluated by the guest based on the behavior of the employee;

2) Insensitivity. Hotel service is unlike any other service. Services are intangible, they cannot be evaluated until they are consumed, they exist only in the process of service and consumption;

- 3) The impossibility of storing, collecting and storing the product (service) produced by the hotel. The hotel product is designed to meet current consumption. If the services are not provided on time and with good quality, the hotel's revenue opportunities will be lost and they will not be restored;
- 4) Change of quality (non-permanence). The hospitality industry is characterized by variability, the quality of which depends on who provides the service and under what conditions. The state of the service provider during service delivery can have a strong impact on the quality of the service. A single person may provide excellent customer service today, and poor customer service tomorrow for any number of reasons (e.g. bad mood, family problems, etc.). Fluctuations in service and fluctuating quality are the main reasons for customer complaints against the hotel industry;
- 5) Seasonality of demand and need. Hotel services are subject to seasonal fluctuations. Demand and demand for hotel products (accommodation and other services) can fluctuate daily, weekly or seasonally. For example, most tourists are on vacation in the summer, and accordingly, the demand for hotel services increases significantly during this period;
- 6) Interdependence of hotel services and travel (visit) purposes. Tour operators and travel agents to sell hotel products actions have a great impact, because it is the hotel business that is very closely connected with tourist activity;
- 7) The dependence of the volume of sales of hotel services on a number of factors: location of the hotel; ease of service; service level and variety; hotel image; rates and prices; range of services, etc.

Tourism is the economic, social, cultural, political, rapid development of the country. It leads to an increase in reputation. Uzbekistan has the same potential as Europe in terms of tourism. But underutilizing this potential means missing out on development.

We need to increase additional services in our hotels. The main of them is the currency exchange service, which is always encountered by tourists. They should be able to exchange their currency for Uzbek soums at any time. The more quickly and qualitatively the service requested by the client is performed, the more the client will want to visit the hotel again, and the hotel will have its regular client. Hotel business is one of the most promising and profitable industries today. The internationalization of the economy and the rapid development of the tourism industry have increased the interest of businessmen and tourists in the services provided in the segment of hotels and hotels, and accordingly, the need for skilled workers is increasing. Attracting this direction as a business proposition, owning a hotel is prestigious and profitable. It should be noted that many are attracted by this opportunity for career growth in the hotel business - for ordinary positions, employers often do not require employees to have any special knowledge or skills (these all can be obtained in the course of work), while serious demands are placed on the management team. It's no secret that professions in the hotel industry are very diverse, because the system defines a large number of specialties - everyone is in the hotel business - from technical staff to direct management - managers, administrators, managers, etc. actively participates. In addition, specialties in the hotel industry are provided by waiters, cooks, maids. In short, everyone can find something to enjoy in this type of activity, because the professions in the hotel business are very diverse.

As mentioned above, in most cases there are no serious requirements for service staff, but this does not mean that everyone can find a job in a hotel or hotel. For example, knowledge of a foreign language is often required, which is already a feature of working in the hotel business. In addition, service personnel in other activities do not need to know a foreign language. About senior employees, then education plays a very big role here, because building a successful hotel or organizing effective employees is a matter that requires training. At the same time,

the presence of a diploma in hotel business does not guarantee successful work for the graduate, because the employer has not only the "shell", but also the practical skills, knowledge and skills of the potential employee. Many hotels offer courses for this purpose.

Institutes of hotel business in Moscow offer many areas where you can specialize in hotel business, but studying there is not always convenient and cheap [13-30]. To meet the needs of guests, you must first know what they expect from your hotel. You can find out by asking your guests for their feedback. If you know what they want in advance, you can act according to their wishes and you will try to exceed them. If the guests have high expectations from the hotel, but the services of your hotel do not match them, this can be the cause of dissatisfaction of your guests.

Secondly, hotel staff must strictly observe cleanliness and hygiene. Especially in the current pandemic situation, the cleanliness of the hotel room is a part of the hotel's reputation. Viruses can remain on every object in the hotel. Because different people enter and leave the hotel and touch different surfaces. For this reason, it is advisable to clean frequently touched objects with disinfectants and carry out general disinfection. Even before the pandemic, cleanliness and hygiene were one of the important factors determining the quality of hotel service. The pandemic conditions required the hotel staff to focus on this factor. Post-pandemic customers also prefer to make sure that a hotel meets sanitation standards before making a hotel decision.

Reference:

1. Aliev , A. , & Musaeva , M. Z. _ K. _ (2021). SYSTEM Zashchity BIOMETRICHESKIY DANNYX . Academic research in educational sciences , 2 (4), 393-396.
2. Aliyev, AA (2021). SISTEMY ZAshchITY BIOMETRICHESKIY DANNYX. Scienceweb academic papers collection .

3. Ismailov Sh. M., Abdusalilov S., Aliev A. ALGORITHM FOR DETERMINATION OF GEOMETRIC AND MECHANICAL PARAMETERS OF RODERS WITH OPTIONAL CROSS-SECTION // Results of National Scientific Research . - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 4. - S. 49-56.
4. Ayubjon son, AA (2022). CONCEPT OF FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES AND TYPES OF UALR. Academic Research , 1 (4), 64-69.
5. Ayubjon oglu AA PRINCIPLES OF FINANCIAL INNOVATION //Academic Research. – 2022. - Volume 1. – No. 4. - S. 70-73.
6. Ayubjon son AA, Islamjon I. SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS SOFTWARE IN THE BANKING FIELD //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS". - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 1. - S. 67-73.
7. Ibrahimjon ogle II, Ayubjon ogle AA THEORETICAL BASICS OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND RISKS ANALYSIS IN INFORMATION SECURITY //Results of national scientific research. - 2022. - T. 1. – no. 4. – S. 39-44.